

Development of transversal skills in an extracurricular academic research project through active learning in healthcare - a case study

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Abstract

Active learning has been widely used by engineering courses to boost the absorption of knowledge through the transition from theoretical content to practical contexts. The idea defended by much research is based on the anticipation of professional life, experienced in the first years as an engineer, for the undergraduate period. Increasingly, engineers are expected to have skills related to solving real company problems, such as eliminating waste, rework, excessive spending, and unnecessary steps in processes. Given this, this paper aims to evaluate how the application of Lean Healthcare tools in the context of a research project contributes to the development of active learning, and, consequently, to the professional practice of the students involved. To this end, a case study was executed in a hospital organization, to list the advantages and challenges faced during this academic experience, and moreover, the main skills and knowledge acquired by students. In addition, aspects of the active learning methodology used are highlighted, more specifically, the Problem and Project Based Learning (PBL) method. The results point to or develop transversal skills, greater involvement, and a sense of responsibility on the part of the students. Lastly, it was observed a great adaptability of the students to the experienced scope increases.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Lean healthcare; Project Based Learning; Problem based learning

1 Introduction

Several universities around the world have been looking for new teaching methodologies to prepare their students to face real experiences. Engineering courses are constantly challenged to innovate their teaching methods, and therefore, undergo extensive changes towards the development of skills and competencies (Andersson, 2015).

In the search for alternative teaching methods that differ from the traditional ones, that is focused on the teacher and the classes are mostly theoretical, the number of studies with approaches focused on the Problem and Project Based Learning (PBL) is growing. This active teaching-learning method aims to offer students opportunities to develop their skills and competencies, through the execution of projects that center on real challenges and problems (Elahi, 2019).

The idea defended by studies related to this type of learning is based on anticipating the students' professional experience, aiming to stimulate the development of skills related to real problems faced in organizations (Carvalho, 2016).

Although these methodologies have been applied in the most diverse contexts, the vast majority of studies are centered on research projects and in the classroom, guided by teachers and having the student as the main element (Althoff, Silva, Milhomem, & Reis, 2019).

There is a large scientific literature on studies dedicated to assessing the skills developed through active methodologies (Althoff et al., 2019; Natsis, Papadopoulous, & Obwegeser, 2018; Jacques, Bissey, & Martin, 2016; Krelová, Krpálek, & Kolarová, 2015; Projektové vyučování, 2011; Králová & Novák, 2014). However, it was not found any study which sets out to investigate the links between advantages, challenges and competencies developed through extracurricular and curricular research projects.

The Industrial Engineering undergraduate program at the University of Brasilia (UNB) promotes teaching through disciplines called Production Systems Projects (PSP) which have Problem and Project Based Learning (PBL) approaches. In addition, the course also reconciles theory and practice through extracurricular projects developed in partnership with public or private organizations from the most varied sectors.

In such context, considering the identified gap in the literature, the main objective of this article is to evaluate how the execution of an extracurricular research project, focusing on the application of Lean Healthcare tools as an active learning approach, contributes to the development of competencies of the students involved. Furthermore, such competencies are compared to those developed by the same students in the PSPs disciplines over the course in Industrial Engineering at UNB.

To enable this study, this research was structured in five sections: the first section introduces the study; the second presents the bibliographic review; the third describes the method used in the study; the fourth presents the case study and, lastly, the fifth section exposes the conclusions. Hopefully, the results found in this study may contribute to the reformulation of active methodologies applied to contexts of intra and extracurricular academic research projects.

2 Active Learning Methodology and Research Projects

Active methodologies can be applied in different contexts, especially in research projects and classroom, by the use of different learning elements, such as workshops, work groups, peer-tutoring sessions, active group dynamics, oral presentation, seminars (Althoff et al., 2019; Natsis et al., 2018; Jacques et al., 2016; Krelová et al., 2015).

All around the world, engineering universities are often challenged to propose new teaching methods to find better ways of assessing students' competencies and improve the educational process. In this context, research projects and their management are one of the most effective ways to assess curricular and cross-curricular competencies developed by students (Jacques et al., 2016).

The literature indicates a wide application of active methodologies in research projects, showing different results obtained. According to Fox, Blake, & Jacobs (2018), research projects are important to students since they are designed to develop the skills needed for experimental design, data collection and statistical analysis.

Natsis et al. (2018), Baluarte-Araya (2020), Lozano, & Trillo-Lado (2015) e Elahi (2019) relate a research project experience developed over a discipline of a university program (course-based research project), where students work on a complex research project and are expected to submit a report at the end of the semester (Mena, Schmitz, & McLaughlin, 2015). Students have revealed that their participation in research projects during undergraduate Engineering programs led them to improve their skills to achieve a much more comprehensive view of the problems and how to analyze them (Murray, Matsuno, Montes, & Bejarano, 2015).

On the other hand, Althoff et al. (2019) explore a research project developed through a cooperation between a public organization and a university. Overall, research projects are used to resolve complex problems in real procedures' practice (Kovac, & Stare, 2014).

Kogtikov, Dukhanov, & Bochenina (2016) confirm the benefits of the students' engagement in transdisciplinary projects. Fox et al. (2018) also ratify that combining the output from multiple research projects has also proven an effective approach in many studies.

Among the active methodologies, Problem and Project Based Learning (whose acronym is PBL) is one of the most widespread (Bessa, Santos & Duarte, 2019; Fernandes, Fuchter Júnior, Daleffe, Fritzen, & Alves de Sousa, 2020). The PBL provides the development of several competencies related to three aspects: cognitive learning, content, and collaborative learning (Du, Su, & Liu, 2013). Cognitive learning assumes that learning is organized around problems and involves the following skills: problem-solving, project management, contextual analysis, and presentation skills. Content is related to interdisciplinary learning and includes disciplinary knowledge, interdisciplinary skills, and information management. In turn, collaborative learning is associated to team-organized learning and involves collaboration and knowledge sharing, communication (oral and written) and

project management and planning. In short, PBL, as a teaching and learning method, can successfully facilitate participative learning, critical reflection, systemic thinking, and creativity (Du et al., 2013).

The benefits of this methodology are quoted in several works and mention elements such as it links theory to practice, in order to be used in real life; it involves challenging questions and problems; stimulates creativity (students present their own ideas and solutions) to solve problems, which can be approached in different ways; it is student-centered; generates learning through experience; seeks to develop work and study habits; develops a sense of responsibility on the part of the students; promote student involvement in decision-making and problem-solving; develops self-confidence, allows teamwork; develops human relationships and a sense of responsibility; generates a result / final product; the teacher acts mainly in the role of advisor (Projektové vyučování, 2011; Králová & Novák, 2014; Krelová, et al., 2015).

The literature points other types of active learning methods that may or not be used in conjunction with PBL. Among them, we can mention the TBL (team-based learning), a strategy that aims to create opportunities and gain benefits by working in small learning groups. Some skills that TBL seeks to develop are encouraging active participation, acquiring notions of self-management, stimulating the exchange of experiences among participants, and promoting involvement in the team's collaborative skills (Althoff et al, 2019).

Table 1 below presents relevant studies (the most cited studies) that address skills developed in research projects carried out using several active learning methodologies.

Table 1. Relevant studies and developed skills.

References	Active Learning Methodology	Developed skills
Du, X; Su, L; Liu, J (2013)	Problem Based Learning	Participative learning, critical reflection, systemic thinking, creativity, and cultural awareness
Jacques, S; Bissey, S; Martin, A (2016)	Problem Based Learning	Autonomy, creativity, openness, collaboration. responsibility.
Murray, V; Matsuno, C; Montes, H; Bejarano, A (2015)	Project Based Learning	Leadership, teamwork, communication skills, creativity, proactivity.
Thomas, I; Depasquale, J (2016)	Problem Based Learning	Systems thinking, Anticipatory, Normative, Strategic and Interpersonal competencies (five key competencies identified as important to sustainability professionals)
Adams, J; Kaczmarczyk, S; Picton, P; & Demian, P (2010)	Problem Based Learning	Problem-solving skills and creativity related to engineering.
Letouze, P; de Souza, J; da Silva, VM (2016)	Project Based Learning	Active role in choosing tools and strategies. Responsibility to make choices, propose solutions and to defend them.

Despite the countless benefits, active methodologies also bring common challenges. According to Yasin, Rahman, & Ahmad (2012), monitoring students' learning is a major challenge in the Problem-oriented Project-based Learning (POPBL) method, since the use of pencil and paper tests is not a good evaluation approach. Therefore, they proposed a portfolio based on journal reflection as a means of monitoring students' learning. While monitoring their learning, coaching, and giving feedback are seen more appropriate. Krelová et al. (2015) also point out the challenge of assessing student performance in the Problem and Project Based Learning (PBL) approach. Kaur (2010) cites alternative assessment modes for active methodologies such as journal writing, classroom observation and conferencing, and self-assessment.

Shekhar, Prince, Finelli, Demonbrun and Waters (2018) argue that active learning requires additional participation from students, which often conflicts with their expectations, resulting in resistance to participate in the active learning exercises. Krelová et al. (2015) also point out another challenge related to teachers who do not have enough teaching skills for project-based learning implementation.

Du et al. (2013), in a study which aimed to understand and analyse culture change toward a sustainability curriculum that employs PBL, list challenges around its implementation: how to change the existing grading system, how to provide both teaching staff and students' with prior knowledge about the new PBL methods, how to gain institutional support, and how to change the broader society and cultural values.

3 Active Learning Methodology in Industrial Engineering at University of Brasília

The Industrial Engineering's program at University of Brasília presents an innovative curriculum, by offering seven regular disciplines and one eventually offered, labelled Production Systems Projects (PSP) which have a Problem and Project Based Learning (PBL) approach, along the program twelve semesters length (Monteiro, Reis, Silva, & Souza, 2017).

These disciplines were created as a way to foster the development of new competencies in students (e.g., problem-solving skills, autonomy, creativity and teamwork) through real-world problem-solving supported by specific project management methodologies (Barbalho, Reis, Bittencourt, Leão, & Silva, 2017). Each of the subjects has anchoring courses, which are taught at the same academic semester, promoting support of teaching technical content (Reis, Mariano, Silva, Amoras, & Moysés, 2019).

The anchoring courses consist of: Information Systems in Production Engineering (SIEP), Production Planning and Control (PCP), Production Quality Management (GQP), Product Engineering (EP) and Strategic Management (GE), each one related to a PSP discipline (Reis et al., 2019).

The results of this approach are mentioned in several studies (Barbalho et al., 2017; Monteiro et al., 2017; Reis, Barbalho, & Zanette, 2017; Reis, Barbalho, de Araújo, Brito, Ishihara, & Teixeira., 2018; Reis et al., 2019). It stimulates students' learning by offering them the opportunity to search for solutions (Barbalho et al., 2017).

The projects developed in these disciplines are based on problems faced by real-world public and private organization. In each semester, students are stimulated to study a new range of themes which support the development of these projects. In turn, the projects allow students to face challenges, solve problems, make decisions based on data and produce results through management skills, soft skills, among others (Monteiro et al., 2017).

In addition, the University of Brasília also develops extracurricular research projects, involving problems of public and private organizations from the most diverse branches of activity. Professors, researchers and undergraduate, master's and doctoral students work together as a way of solving these real problems of organizations and to encourage active learning of those involved.

4 Methods

The study consists of exploratory research with qualitative approach developed through a case study (Yin, 2011). It was carried out in the context of a research project in a hospital environment and focused on two phases of the project (planning and execution).

Throughout each of them, it was evaluated the contribution of this academic experience as an active learning approach for the development of the professional practice of the students involved. The advantages and challenges were evaluated, as well as the skills developed, and knowledge acquired. It was done through three stages:

STAGE 1) Bibliographic review: in order to identify research projects used as a form of active learning and establish relationships between research projects and methodologies used in undergraduate disciplines - PBL (Problem and Project Based Learning);

STAGE 2) Collection of the students' opinion (by applying a questionnaire adapted from Reis et al. (2018) with 37 competencies): in order to capture the report of the students involved in the research project regarding the challenges, difficulties and learning provided by the learning experience at each stage;

STAGE 3) Students' perspective analysis: in order to extract information from the students' report and their perception of how the characteristics of the extracurricular academic research project resemble as active learning disciplines.

The bibliographic review (presented in section 2) was performed in Scopus®, Web of Science (WoS®) and ScienceDirect databases. The keywords were used in the following format: ("research project") AND ("skills" OR "competencies") AND (("active learning" OR "active methodology" OR "problem based learning" OR "project based learning" OR "pbl" OR "pjbl"). Initially, duplicate articles were eliminated and then, by reading their abstracts, 25 articles that best fit the context studied were selected.

The collection of the students' opinion was done through a structured questionnaire, released through Google Forms platform between 06/12/2020 to 06/14/2020, with 15 questions (section 4.2) to evaluate learning aspects and experiences lived throughout the extracurricular academic research project.

5 Case Study

5.1 Context

The case study describes an academic research project context which was developed in a public hospital organization. The project consisted of a study and application of Lean Healthcare principles in order to formulate a methodology for improving hospital processes.

The hospital organization faces major challenges, which are essentially related to creating an environment favorable for continuous improvement, working with the correct references of procedures and management and, planning improvement implementation processes.

By this context, the objectives of the research project were outlined in to build the organization's Value Chain, identify and prioritize critical macro processes, build the Value Stream Map for one of the prioritized macro processes and propose action plans and methods for monitoring and continuous improvement.

The construction of the Value Chain enabled the understanding of the hospital's macro processes and provided a holistic view of the Institution. Based on the prioritization of critical macro processes and meetings with the hospital managers, it was decided that the Value Stream Map would be built in the hospital inpatient sector. In an extensive literature review, the VSM was widely mentioned as an important tool used in Lean Healthcare context. The flows of patients, materials and information were mapped for the flow of inpatient sector. In addition, the process lead time was measured, and the inefficiencies related to each waste of time were identified. The VSM showed the main problems faced in the inpatient sector activities, and thus, short, medium and long-term action plans were established. Most of the action plans involved multidisciplinary meetings mediated by the students, where the health professionals involved discussed how they could turn their activities more efficient. Some short-term improvements were implemented, provoking great satisfaction for the professionals involved and for the hospital's managers.

The implementation of the action plans to solve problems were monitored by the project team and the progressive solution to the problems, previously identified, provided improvements to the hospital inpatient processes.

The research project lasted 12 months and was developed through five phases: initiation, planning, execution, monitoring and controlling and closure. Only planning and execution are part of the case study' scope.

The case study was carried out from the questionnaire application to the nine students of the Industrial Engineering program at University of Brasilia (seven undergraduate and two master's degree students) under the guidance of three PhD professors, who participated in the research project.

5.2 Student Experience Report

The student experience report sought to list the developed competencies, faced difficulties and challenges throughout the phases of the extracurricular research project; and to evaluate differences between aspects of the research project and the curricular projects developed in the PSP disciplines of the Industrial Engineering program at UNB. An instrument for data collection was elaborated, whose aspects are presented in this item, through the qualitative analysis of the students' responses.

The collected data indicate that all students involved in the extracurricular research project have already taken at least one PSP discipline. In addition, it was identified that 66.7% of these students have already participated in other extracurricular research projects. The competencies developed in each phase of the project (planning and execution) were evaluated and classified into three dimensions: Management, Soft skills and Technical, according to Table 2.

Table 2 shows the result of the descriptive statistics on the students' responses. For each set of competencies (management, soft skills and technical) students pointed out which ones they thought they had developed in the planning and execution phases.

Table 2. List of 37 competencies developed during research project

Management	Soft Skills		Technical				
	Planning	Execution	Planning	Execution			
1. Schedule Formulation	44,4%	66,7%	13. Communication	77,8%	29. Value Chain elaboration	22,2%	77,8%
2. Scope Definition	44,4%	77,8%	14. Formal Presentation	55,6%	30. Multicriteria Analysis	11,1%	55,6%
3. Definition of working subgroups	66,7%	77,8%	15. Building Trust in the Team	77,8%	31. VSM elaboration	22,2%	77,8%
4. Stakeholder Identification	77,8%	77,8%	16. Conflict Management	55,6%	32. Process Flowchart	22,2%	33,3%
5. Stakeholder Analysis (expectations, power and interest)	77,8%	55,6%	17. Troubleshooting	66,7%	33. A3 elaboration	11,1%	55,6%
6. Development of Communication Artefacts	44,4%	66,7%	18. Relationship Building	77,8%	34. Graph Theory application	0,0%	22,2%
7. Risk Analysis	44,4%	33,3%	19. Self-Management	77,8%	35. Mudge diagram application	22,2%	66,7%
8. Strategic Thought	66,7%	77,8%	20. Self Confidence	66,7%	36. Data Analysis	33,3%	77,8%
9. Monitoring and Control of Project Indicators	22,2%	22,2%	21. Collaboration	77,8%	37. SIPOC tool application	33,3%	77,8%
10. Monitoring and Control of	44,4%	66,7%	22. Creativity	55,6%			
11. Political and Cultural Knowledge	44,4%	33,3%	23. Proactivity	55,6%			
12. Result Orientation	55,6%	88,9%	24. Leadership	33,3%			
			25. Negotiation	33,3%			
			26. Teamwork	77,8%			
			27. Ethics and Values	44,4%			
			28. Adaptability	66,7%			

Regarding management competencies, in the planning phase, with 77.8% of the responses, *Stakeholder Identification* (4) and *Stakeholder Analysis (expectations, power and interest)* (5) were indicated as the main competencies developed by students. In the execution phase, with 88.9% of the responses, *Result Orientation* (12) was indicated. For soft skills, in the planning phase, with 77.8% of the responses, *Communication* (13), *Building Trust in the Team* (15), *Relationship Building* (18), *Self-Management* (19), *Collaboration* (21) and *Teamwork* (26) were indicated as the main competencies developed. In the execution phase, with 88.9% of the responses, *Communication* (13), *Formal Presentation*, *Troubleshooting* (17), *Relationship Building* (18) and *Teamwork* (26) were indicated. Finally, for technical competencies, in the planning phase, it was not observed the development of many competencies since technical competencies are usually developed in the execution phase. On the other side, in the execution phase, it was observed the development of various Lean Healthcare related skills, such as *Value Chain elaboration* (29), *VSM elaboration* (21), *Data Analysis* (36) and *SIPOC tool application* (37), with 77.8% of the responses.

Difficulties and challenges perceived in each phase of the extracurricular project (planning and execution)

For the students, in the planning phase of the research project, they experienced difficulties related to ambiance in the project, as the students only started their activities in the project after the beginning of the partnership with the hospital and did not participate in the phase that preceded the agreement, in which the work plan was elaborated (initiation phase); the engagement of stakeholders, as the importance of the project was not passed from the strategic level of the hospital to the operational one; unavailability of the stakeholders; adaptation to teamwork, due to the fact that the team was getting to know each other; adaptation to the content required by the activities, due to the absence of previous contact with some subjects; difficulty in understanding the deliveries, due to lack of knowledge about the project's scope.

In the execution phase, students experienced challenges related to the following aspects: to approach hospital staff, as many of them had difficulty understanding the purpose of the project; intense schedule of on-site activities; large volume of acquired information; difficulty in mediation between health professionals involved; to associate the application of multidisciplinary tools (SIPOC tool - acronym of Supplier, Input, Process, Output, Customer -, data mining tools, graph theory, multicriteria analysis, among others); to maintain a constant alignment between the team; to maintain communication and alignment between stakeholders; to reconcile expectations and what will actually be delivered; difficulty on scheduling some on-site meetings.

Difficulties and challenges experienced in the extracurricular project and not experienced in curricular project (PSP discipline)

Regarding the difficulties experienced in the extracurricular research project that were not previously experienced, it can be mentioned: changes in scope; to maintain a pace of productivity, as there were many contents; communication and alignment between stakeholders; difficulty in scheduling on-site meetings.

Some students stated that they did not have any additional difficulties because the PGP (Project Management Plan), in PSP disciplines, is always carried out by the student and for execution, they claim that they have experienced the same difficulties.

An important view is that in PSP disciplines, there is not the same charge from customers because if there are no results, there will be no major problems. In the extracurricular research project, there was a contract and the payment of a research grant, so the results needed to be delivered. For some students, the responsibility was immensely greater during the extracurricular project than in curricular projects done in PSP disciplines, as there were deadlines and commitment to the customer. Furthermore, in the extracurricular research project, students feel that they are charged and constantly monitored for the execution of activities.

Evaluation of the difference between the extracurricular research project and the curricular research project (PSP discipline) in the following factors

(i) Schedule

Students consider that the schedule of an extracurricular project is much longer, and can last for years, while projects developed in PSP discipline take place in just 1 semester. Thus, the challenge of making a schedule in an extracurricular project is greater, given the scope's dimension; the time of execution; the need to align with different stakeholders; the better definition and constancy of deliveries.

In addition, some students consider the extracurricular project timeline to be inflexible, but with more execution time, and the schedule is discussed among all of the teamwork.

For students, in projects developed in PSP disciplines, the schedule usually follows a period of one semester, regardless of the complexity of the project's scope, thus they were easier to be followed.

(ii) Quality of deliveries

Students consider the quality of deliveries much higher in the extracurricular research project, when compared to projects of PSP disciplines, because time for planning and execution is much longer in the first case; it is based on a contract with a real customer and the deliveries are better prepared and professional.

For students, in projects on PSP disciplines the quality of deliveries must meet the requirements necessary for the student to be approved and has a study bias.

Other students think that the quality of both must follow a standard of excellence. But in the extracurricular project, charging is higher because it involves a formal schedule and expectations of more people.

(iii) Interaction with stakeholders

For students, the interaction with stakeholders is higher and more organized in the extracurricular research project because the project duration is longer, requiring more meetings, validation and presentation of results, on-site visits, etc.

Students believe that in PSP disciplines, because they are "free of charge" projects, a little less formal, developed in less time, there is less charging from stakeholders and also less interaction, where students go in search of the client.

(iv) Type of performance evaluation

The students' perception of performance evaluation brings interesting aspects. They state that in the extracurricular project performance evaluation suffered a greater impact from stakeholders, since all deliveries were evaluated by them, while in the projects of PSP disciplines many deliveries are only evaluated by teachers. In addition, in PSP disciplines, teachers are rarely evaluated by stakeholders, unlike an extracurricular project where teachers are also evaluated.

For students, the performance evaluation on the extracurricular project came from the client, what made the evaluation more faithful to the job market and the efforts were really perceived by project leaders. Furthermore, the assessment was based on the productivity of each member (individual) and on their own self-assessment, built from their perception of the work done, teammate opinions, criticism, or praise from clients.

In PSP disciplines, students argue that the group is usually evaluated as a whole, and the motivation of the students is around the grade. Moreover, they believe that the PEER evaluation, which happens in some PSP disciplines, does not always reflect the performance of the others. Students do not like to misjudge their "peers", even though they haven't worked. In extracurricular projects it is different, you get a research grant for what you do, and the result ends up being charged in a more formal way.

(v) Training

The number of training in the extracurricular project is considered by the students to be greater than in the PSP disciplines, which in many cases do not even accomplish, there is only guidance. In addition, anchor disciplines do not always address topics of interest in the exact moment the student needs the content. In the extracurricular project, the training is more intense and contributed to the best development of the project, resulting in better quality of deliveries.

(vi) Learning

For some students, the extracurricular project brought many more lessons, due to its duration; to the deepening that must be done on the subjects to accomplish deliveries; to the great number of research and training carried out and to the need to overcome new challenges.

They mentioned that learning in PSP disciplines is based on trial and error, while in the extracurricular project, there was time for students to prepare themselves.

Many agree that both experiences are significant. It is usually through PSP disciplines that students have the first contact with real world problems. In the extracurricular research project, the learning is more intense, the training raises the level of work and can be classified as a level closer to a graduated engineer.

(vii) Preparing for the job market

According to the students, the extracurricular research project provides greater preparation for the market job (without excluding the importance of PSP discipline, mentioned as very positive), a real experience, due to the formal nature of the contract, the experiences lived, through intense interaction with the customer, through the demand for higher quality of delivery, through a schedule that must be strictly adhered to, by the charging of stakeholders.

(viii) Interdisciplinary technical learning aspect

For students, extracurricular and curricular projects (developed in PSP disciplines) drive interdisciplinary technical learning, but PSP disciplines give a lot of technical baggage that applies to the extracurricular research projects.

As already mentioned, students, in the extracurricular project, needed to seek the knowledge to outline the deliverables, experiencing a very large interdisciplinary technical learning, due also to the broad scope of the project where students needed to know a little bit of everything.

Other students reported that in PSP disciplines they need to go in search of all the tools they needed to use, there were no training, which, in some way, develops autonomy.

6 Conclusion

Active learning approaches bring, with different focuses, ways to develop skills in students that go beyond technical knowledge. Engineering education brings the challenge of keeping up with technological developments and preparing students for the job market with the required skills.

This research presents a case study that involves the participation of undergraduate and master students in an extracurricular academic research project, developed in the hospital environment, with a focus on application of Lean Healthcare tools to improve the studied processes. As an active learning experience, we sought to report learning and to identify transversal skills developed in this learning context and compare it with what was experienced in the disciplines called PSP, which involve active learning during students' graduation.

As a result of the students' reports, a complementary relationship was observed between the experiences reported in PSP disciplines and extracurricular projects, as if the PSP disciplines were an initial step and the extracurricular projects configured an experience closer to the real world.

Students reported a lot of learning in PSP disciplines, teamwork, short schedules, narrower scope, less interaction with external agents (customers) and greater flexibility regarding deliveries. For the extracurricular project, they reported more experience with the customers; the realization of training; broader scope; longer schedule, but not very flexible; more rigorous evaluations, but self-assessment seems a natural process; more charging and more challenges.

The skills developed in each phase were evaluated and classified into three dimensions: Management, Soft skills and Technical. First, while the main competencies developed during the planning phase were related to stakeholder identification and analysis, the execution phase showed that the main competence developed was result orientation. Second, it was observed the development of the same competencies in both phases, such as communication, relationship building and teamwork, although during the planning phase, students related the development of building trust in the team, collaboration and self-management skills. Also, during the execution phase, students related the development of formal presentation and troubleshooting skills. Finally, it was observed that most of the competencies were developed in the execution phase, considering that it requires more in-depth technical knowledge.

In fact, extracurricular research projects are a form of active methodology which comes closer to what the student will face after graduation, with similar challenges to the real professional practice. Also, for master's students, learning was perceived, and transversal skills were developed that could boost their careers.

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